

MAKING SENSE OF MEDIATING ANALYSIS OF EMPLOYEE AWARENESS AND TRAINING IN RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN E-HRM PRACTICES AND ORGANIZATIONAL-EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE USING SEM ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

The aim of the descriptive research study was to know the mediating effect of employee awareness and the employee training in relationship between the various digital human resource management practices and its impact on the organizational and employee performance. **Findings:** The outcome of the research witnessed that the employee awareness and the employee training are essential aspects to bring the sophisticated changes with respect to human resource management practices by implementation of digitalization practices in the organization. **Research Design/Methodology/Approach:** The researcher has developed a structured open-ended questionnaire to collect data from various respondents. Applied descriptive and inferential statistics like: Mean, SD, Correlation, Regression, Confirmatory Factor analysis, structural equation modelling. **Novelty:** The model developed with the two different new constructs as mediators in between the digital human resource management practices and the outcome of organizational-environmental performance and at the middle, employee awareness and the training. **Social Relevance:** The outcome of the research can be applied where; the need arises to implement the digital human resource management practices to bring the advancements in the organizational performance. **Generalizability:** The outcome of the research can be generalized under any circumstances where, the similar circumstances arise to implement E-HRM practices in the organization. **Novelty:** It is a novel model where two different constructs used as mediators like: employee awareness and employee training in between facilitating factors of E-HRM and organizational and employee performance in the organization. **Type of the Research:** It is a descriptive research design by nature.

Keywords: E-HRM, Digital HRM practices, Electronic HRM practices, Digital human resource management practices, Digitalization of HRM practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

As it is witnessed from the sources that the digital human resource management practices can bring the transformational changes in the organization. Especially, the measurement of employee's performance by setting clear goals followed by the availability of employee database facilitates for comparing the individual performance and making assessments and the employee self-service (ESS) and managers self-service(MSS) and the all sorts of employee transactions like: salaries, EPF, TAX returns, E-Learning and the decision-making based on the availability of data base and the online recruitment and selection also facilitates for minimizing the cost associated with that and even can attract the global talent across the world. The managers self-service will facilitates to know employee related information and for effective decision-making. In the overall, the digital/electronic human resource management practices will facilitates to take effective decision-making in the competitive phenomena. It helps to meet the contemporary changes of the world. Therefore, there is a need to take the advantage of electronic human resource management practices and should provide the training to individuals to make them to familiarize to the digital human resource management practices in the organization.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

It is evident from the analysis that, the digital human resource management practices will bring sophisticated changes in the organization. Especially, it will reduces the cost of HRM operations followed by can introduce the green HRM practices by minimizing the usage of paper work in the organization ^[1]. It is also witnessed the same, facilitates to perform many activities like application tracking, digital training, online recruitment facilitates the less cost of HRM practices in the contemporary phenomena. Therefore, it is evident that the electronic human resource management practices will facilitates for reduction of cost ^[2]. It is observed that the usage and the implementation pattern of digital/electronic HRM practices are different in between the Indian and European countries as the employees are less aware about the E-HRM practices in the organization. Therefore, it is emergence that the Indian firms need to implement the E-HRM practices and should provide training and development practices followed by need to create awareness about the digital human resource management practices in the organization ^[3]. The implementation of E-HRM practices in the organization will reduce the burden on the HR staff followed by will create the reliable and transparent source to the employees to trace the employee related details through portal ^[4]. It is also proved that the usage of digitally maintaining records through the digitalization practices especially in hospitals will facilitates to maintain the employee records and patent records in a systematic manner ^[5] followed by explained about the role of e-training and its importance in the organization rather manual employee training. The digital training shows a systematic training will facilitates and brings the effectiveness in the employee training in the organization. Therefore, it is witnessed from the analysis that, the digital HRM practices will bring sophisticated changes in the organization ^[6]. The greater dependency on online recruitment and selection facilitated a lot depend more on social networking sites like: Face book, Twitter, LinkedIn ^[7,8]. The online recruitment will facilitates to wide pool of database can be generated

by few actions by implanting the electronic recruitment practices in the organizations^[9]. It will also prove that based on the demographic factors the usage pattern and connection with the digital HRM transactions will change. Therefore, it depends up on various demographic factors of individuals^[10]. Therefore, from all directions the digital human resource management practices will bring the tremendous changes in the organization and it will facilitate to enhance the knowledge of individuals. Therefore, the present research will explain a lot about how, the mediating variables like: employee awareness and employee training will facilitates and acts as a mediating role in between the digital human resource management practices and the organizational and employee performance in the organization. The research GAP was identified there is no such kind of study where there are certain mediating variables like: employee awareness and employee training may facilitate to strengthen the relationship between the E-HRM practices and the organizational and employee performance in the contemporary phenomena.

Objectives:

- ✚ The present study is to know the mediating effect of employee awareness and training with respect to E-HRM practices and Organizational-employee performance.
- ✚ To study whether the model is declaring the goodness of fit index in the contemporary scenario.
- ✚ To provide a good model for the implementation of E-HRM practices in the organization.

Statement of the Problem:

The research title entitled to “Making sense of Mediating Analysis of Employee awareness and Training in Relationship between E-HRM Practices and Organizational-Employee Performance using SEM Analysis”. As it is important that the digital human resource management practices and related training and development practices are essential to strengthen organizational and environmental development.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY & DESIGN

It is a descriptive research design by nature. The data collected from various primary and secondary data sources.

Data Sources: The researcher has taken the advantage of both primary and secondary data sources. The primary data sources collected by using the survey methods followed by the secondary data collection has done based on articles which are available from web sources and from other sources.

Sample Size: The researcher has taken sufficient sample size to assess the model in all dimensions. The researcher has developed a structured open ended questionnaire to collect the opinion from various respondents.

Sampling Techniques: Researcher applied both descriptive and inferential statistics for the assessment of the phenomena. The descriptive statistics include the Mean, SD, correlation and regression and other statistics also included they are confirmatory factor analysis and the structural equation modelling algorithm.

Sampling Tool: To assess the model researcher used, SPSS JASP programming concepts to develop and validate the model in a systematic manner.

Hypothesis: Here hypothesis drawn in relationship between the independent and mediating variables followed by the mediating and dependent variables.

H₀ (1): There is a significant positive association between the implementation of digital human resource management practices and the employee awareness.

H₀ (2): There is a significant positive relationship between the implementation of digital human resource management practices and the employee training.

H₀ (3): There is a significant positive relationship between the employee awareness and the organizational-employee performance in the organization.

H₀ (4): There is a significant positive relationship between the organizational performance and the employee training.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The route map of the analysis include, conducting the correlation analysis to the given followed by testing the dependency and independence using Multiple linear regression analysis followed extracting the factors by using the confirmatory factor analysis and the model development with the help of structural equation modelling algorithm and the correlation matrix.

Variable		EP	ER	EM	EL	ES	ED	ET	EAW	OP
1. EP	Pearson's	—								
	p-value	—								
2. ER	Pearson's	0.595 ***	—							
3. EM	Pearson's	0.512 ***	0.51 ***	—						
4. EL	Pearson's	0.691 ***	0.64 ***	0.66 ***	—					
5. ES	Pearson's	0.645 ***	0.49 ***	0.52 ***	0.52 ***	—				
6. ED	Pearson's	0.686 ***	0.57 ***	0.56 ***	0.65 ***	0.58 ***	—			
7. ET	Pearson's	0.64 ***	0.61 ***	0.47 ***	0.64 ***	0.44 ***	0.53 ***	—		
8. EAW	Pearson's	0.136	0.14	0.02	0.01	0.07	0.04	0.06	—	
9. OP	Pearson's	0.108	0.13	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.9 ***	—

* p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001

It is evident from the analysis that there are various types of factors like: Electronic performance, electronic recruitment, and employee self-service and manager self-service, electronic learning, electronic salary, electronic database, electronic training, employee awareness and organizational performance. Therefore, is evident from the analysis that all the factors have shown the significant relationship with the remaining all other factors. The recruitment with performance the correlation value is ($r=0.595$ & $p<.001$) followed by with ESS and MSS the ($r=0.512$ & $p<.001$) and with the learning ($r=0.691$ & $p<.001$) followed by salary with the performance appraisal ($r=0.645$ & $p<.001$) and with the employee database ($r=0.686$ & $p<.001$) and with training ($r=0.640$ & $p<.001$) and with the employee awareness ($r=0.136$ & $p<.001$) and with the organizational performance ($r=0.249$ & $p<.001$) followed by ESS and MSS with the employee recruitment ($r=0.507$ & $p<.001$) and with employee learning ($r=0.636$ & $p<.001$) and with salary ($r=0.488$ & $p<.001$) and with employee database ($r=0.574$ & $p<.001$) and employee Training ($r=0.610$ & $p<.001$) and with employee awareness ($r=0.136$ & $p<.001$). Therefore, it is evident from the analysis that all the factors in the analysis have shown the significant relationship with the remaining all other factors. Therefore, there is no multicollinearity problem in the analysis.

Figure 1: Correlation Matrix of Digital HRM Practices

It is evident from the above matrix that, it includes three phases. It includes the scatter plot matrix followed by the normality of the data study and the correlation values. All the correlation values in the analysis have shown the significant positive relationship with the remaining all other factors and the normality graph also has shown the significant relationship and the data has normally distributed and the scatter plot matrix also explained that all the values in the scatter plot moving from the left to right direction. Therefore, it is witnessed from the analysis that all the factors in the analysis have shown the significant relationship with the remaining all other factors which are included in the analysis.

Table 2: Pearson's Correlations of Digital HRM Practices

Factors of Digital Human Resource Management	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Org_ Performance	4.0174	.62102	115
E_ Performance	4.2130	.53110	115
E_ Recruitment	4.0978	.50404	115
ESS_MSS	4.0217	.61645	115
E_ Learning	4.1696	.55463	115
E_ Salary	4.0674	.54544	115
Emp_ Database	4.1217	.54246	115
E_ Training	4.0957	.55269	115
Emp_ awareness	4.0413	.61943	115

It is evident from the analysis that, all the factors in the analysis have shown the agreed response as the Mean value is above four. Therefore, it tells that the all the factors are having positive impact on the analysis. The organizational performance and its mean value is 4.0174 followed by the SD value is 0.62102 and the organizational performance and its mean value is 4.2130 and its SD value is 0.53110 and the recruitment and the corresponding mean value is 4.0978 and the employee self-service and the manager self-service and its mean value is 4.0217 and its corresponding SD value is 0.61645 and the digital learning and its corresponding mean value is 4.1696 and the SD value is .55463 and the employee awareness and its corresponding mean value is 4.0413 and its SD value is 0.61943. Therefore, it is witnessed from the analysis that all the factors in the analysis have shown the significant positive impact on the analysis.

Table 3: Regression Analysis on Digital HRM Practices

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.900 ^a	.809	.795	.28129	.809	56.207	8	106	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Emp_ awareness, E_ Learning, E_ Salary, E_ Training, ESS_MSS, E_ Recruitment, Emp_ Database, E_ Performance

It is evident from the analysis that, 80.9% of the variance in the dependent variable it is being explained by the list of independent variables like: awareness, online learning, payroll, online

training, employee self-service and manager self-service, recruitment, employee database, employee performance and it has shown the significant relationship with the dependent variable and even the p-value ($p < .001$) has shown the significant relationship. Therefore, it is evident that there is an every unit change in the independent variable, significant change in the dependent variable of employee and organizational performance.

Figure 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis on Digital HRM Practices

It is evident from the diagram that there are four variables in each factor. The Digital performance appraisal (DHRMP1, DHRMP2, DHRMP3, DHRMP4) and the corresponding factor loadings are 0.95, 0.40, 0.50 and 0.40 followed by the digital recruitment (DHRMR1, DHRMR2, DHRMR3, DHRMR4) and its corresponding factor loadings are (0.50, 0.30, 0.30 and 0.57) and the employee pay roll (DHRMS1, DHRMS2, DHRMS3 and DHRMS4) and its corresponding loadings are (0.30, 0.60, 0.56, 0.54) and the digital learning (DHRML1, DHRML2, DHRML3, DHRML4) and the corresponding loadings are (0.49, 0.59, 0.40 and 0.58) and employee database (DATABASE1, DATABASE2, DATABASE3, DATABASE4) and the corresponding loadings are (0.50, 0.48, 0.50 and 0.38) and the employee and the organizational performance (0.90, 0.97, 0.91 and 0.65). Therefore, it is evident from the analysis that all the factors in the analysis have loaded successfully, therefore, it is evident from the analysis, and the confirmatory factor analysis have proved and segregated various factors in the analysis. Further the path analysis can be validated through developing a model. The model comprises of two different effects. They are direct and in-direct effect. The direct effect explains the relationship between the digital human resource management practices and the organizational and the employee performance, whereas the indirect effect and its relationship explains about the facilitating factors of digital human resource management practices followed

by the employee awareness and employee training and the organizational and the environmental performance.

Proposed Model:

Figure 3: The Path Model of Digital HRM Practices

It is evident from the above analysis that there are three different categories of variables in the analysis they are; Independent variables and the mediating variables and the dependent variables. Therefore, there is a two different kinds of effects will come into the picture. They are direct effect and the indirect effect. The model can be assed based on the significant relationship between the variables which are included in the analysis. The confirmatory factor analysis witnessed that there are various types of factors which are extracted from the analysis. The model can be used in practical phenomena where the need arises to assess the customer awareness and training and development and its impact on the dependent variable of organizational performance.

Figure 4: The Path Model of Digital HRM Practices (Measurement)

From the above diagram it is witnessed that the path coefficients between the three different categories of variables like: independent, dependent and mediating variables. The path coefficient between the performance to employee awareness is ($\beta = 0.27$ & $p < .001$) and between recruitment to employee awareness ($\beta = 0.22$ & $p < .001$) and with the employee self-service and the managers self service ($\beta = 0.01$ & $p < .001$) and with employee learning to employee training ($\beta = 0.26$ & $p < .001$) and with employee salary ($\beta = 0.041$ & $p < .001$) and with the employee database ($\beta = 0.01$ & $p < .001$) and it has shown employee database to employee awareness ($\beta = 0.08$ & $p < .001$) and employee awareness to employee performance ($\beta = 0.91$ & $p < .001$). Therefore, it is evident from the analysis that there is a significant relationship among the variables/factors which are included in the analysis. Therefore, it is evident from the analysis that there is a significant direct and indirect relationship among the variables in the analysis which facilitates for effective organizational performance and the employee awareness and the employee training in the organization.

5. CONCLUSION:

Therefore, it is evident from the analysis the new constructs: awareness and training have shown significant difference in the result. As these two constructs are essential to introduce the digital human resource management practices to create awareness about the E-HRM practices followed by need to provide the training facilities to train employees to meet the contemporary situations.

References:

1. Nenwani, P., & Raj, M. E-HRM Prospective in Present Scenario. *International Journal*, 2013, 1(7)
2. Swaroop, K. R, E-HRM and how it will reduce the cost in organisation. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Management Review*, 2012, 1(4), 133-139.
3. Panneerselvem, A. Electronic human resource management, *International journal of multidisciplinary research and modern education*, 2017, 3(1), 55-58.
4. Dr.Rupa Rathee, Innovative e-HRM Practices in IT organizations, *YMER is an International Open Access*, VOLUME 21 : ISSUE 1 (Jan), 2022, pp.605-621.
5. Lakshmi, C. D. Study on E-Hrm Practices in Kovai Medical Center and Hospital,Coimbatore. *Journal of Business Management & Social Sciences Research (JBM&SSR)*, 2014, 3(8), 43-47.
6. Manju, S., & Suresh, B. H, Training Design Interventions and Implications for the Productivity Effectiveness. *Synergy*, 2011, 9(1).
7. Bissola, R. and Imperatori, B, Recruiting Gen Yers Through Social Media: Insights from the Italian Labor Market. In: BONDAROUK, T. and OLIVAS-LUJÁN, M.R. (eds.) *Social Media in Human Resources Management (Advanced Series in Management, Vol. 12)*. Bingley: Emerald Group Publishing Limited, 2014, pp. 59-81.
8. Lecuyer and Pelletier, Exploration of Social Media Capabilities for Recruitment in SMEs: A Multiple Case Study. *HRM 4.0 for Human Centered Organizations*, 23, 2019, pp. 221-239.
9. MOCHI, F., BISSOLA, R., and IMPERATORI, B, Professional and non-professional social media as recruitment tools: The impact on job seekers' attraction and intention to apply. In: BONDAROUK, T., RUËL, H.J.M., and PARRY, E. (eds.) *Electronic HRM in the Smart Era (The Changing Context of Managing People)*. Bingley: Emerald Publishing Limited, 2017, pp. 109-135.
10. Sareen, P, Study of employee satisfaction towards e-HRM system. *European Journal of Applied Business and Management*, 2015, 1(1).